

Factsheet

Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) – A 'hot' Technology for Industrial Transformation

©DLR – Solar Irradiation

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Introduction

Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) is a promising renewable technology that concentrates solar radiation to achieve high solar fluxes and obtain high temperatures. In the case of solar tower systems, large mirrors, known as heliostats, are used to collect sunlight and reflect its rays onto a central solar receiver. By concentrating sunlight, CST can heat up a heat transfer fluid or a particle heat carrier to produce high-temperature heat. This carrier then delivers the thermal power to downstream processes for industrial heating, for driving chemical reactions or for electricity generation (being referred in this case as CSP, concentrated solar power). CST can play a pivotal role in the global push towards **industrial decarbonisation**, especially in hard-to-electrify sectors, and also support the **defossilisation** of the industry by generating renewable feedstocks for the circular economy.

One important application is explored in the EU-funded project PYSOLO (PYrolysis of biomass by concentrated SOLAr pOwer). PYSOLO focuses on harnessing CST-generated process heat for biomass pyrolysis, a heat-intense process that enables the conversion of wood and organic residues into high-value products such as bio-oil, biochar and pyrogas with cost-efficient and high conversion yields.¹

Compared with conventional pyrolysis, which typically relies on combustion of a portion of the pyrolysis products, CST-driven pyrolysis can increase the yield of valuable products while reducing CO₂ emissions. This approach not only offers environmental advantages but also brings economic benefits by making production more efficient and sustainable.

Industrial Applications of CST

CST's unique capability to deliver high-temperature heat makes it suitable for different energy and non-energy purposes:

- **Pyrolysis:** CST provides the necessary heat for the thermochemical transformation of biomass or waste materials into valuable renewable products in an oxygen-free environment.²
- **Process Heat:** Industries such as steel and mining can replace fossil-based heat with CSP-based systems.³
- **Advanced Plastics Recycling:** High temperatures from CSP can enable chemical recycling of plastics, breaking polymers into reusable monomers.⁴
- **Solar Fuels Production:** CST drives endothermic reactions such as water splitting or methane reforming to produce green hydrogen or syngas.⁵
- **Phosphorus and Iron Recovery:** The carbothermal reduction needed for the recovery of phosphorus and iron from molten modified high-phosphorus industrial slag is another endothermic reaction that could be run by CST.⁶
- **Electricity Generation:** CSP with thermal storage allows stable and renewable power supply, complementing photovoltaics and wind.⁷

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Heliostats

Heliostats are moveable mirrors that track the sun with two tracking axes and direct sunlight onto a solar receiver located at the top of a solar tower. Thousands of heliostats can operate in concert to achieve high flux intensities. In future, artificial intelligence will likely support automation of heliostat control.

©DLR – Heliostat Field

Aspects of CSP/CST Technology

- Building a CST/CSP plant requires significant initial investment. The main cost drivers are the heliostat field and the solar tower where the concentrated sunlight is collected.⁹
- CST/CSP offers the chance to operate a plant continuously by integrating a suitable thermal storage which is of specific advantage for chemical process often requiring steady state conditions.
- CST plants are able to provide affordable high temperature heat which is required for high temperature endothermic reactions like those involved in biomass conversion processes.
- CSP plants can be combined with PV plants to deliver renewable electricity in a flexible, continuous and storable manner.
- Like all renewable energy technologies, CST/CSP plants need substantial land areas, especially for the mirror fields. More compact, modular systems tailored to industrial needs are necessary.
- CST/CSP works best in areas with very high levels of Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI), that is, strong and consistent direct sunlight¹⁰ such as Southern Europe, North Africa, the Middle East, parts of the southwestern United States, Chile, and Australia, among others.
- To achieve the best possible concentration of sunlight, the mirrors must remain clean, free of scratches, and properly aligned. This requires regular maintenance, particularly in dusty or sandy environments.¹¹

Regulatory and Policy Context in the EU

The European Union supports the adoption of CST/CSP under several frameworks:

- Renewable Energy Directive (RED II & III): Sets binding targets for renewable energy share, explicitly supporting renewable heating and cooling.¹²
- Green Deal and Fit for 55 Package: Promotes decarbonisation of industry through electrification and renewable heat.¹³
- EU ETS (Emissions Trading System): Provides economic incentives for industrial sectors to adopt low-carbon technologies like CST/CSP.¹⁴
- Horizon Europe: Funds research projects such as PYSOLO to foster innovation in clean energy.¹⁵

Conclusion

CST/CSP is a versatile and powerful renewable solution for the industrial sector, capable of delivering both high temperature heat for downstream processes and/or electricity. Projects like PYSOLO are essential to realise its full potential, addressing integration challenges, and moving Europe towards a carbon-neutral economy. While challenges remain, the combination of strong EU policies, technological progress and industrial integration can make CST/CSP a cornerstone of Europe's green transition.

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Solar Receiver Development and Particle Heat Carriers

Within the PYSOLO project, a major focus lies on the solar receiver, the component that absorbs concentrated sunlight and transforms it into usable heat for the pyrolysis process. The project will design, build and test a rotary kiln solar receiver with different heat carriers, while also developing a detailed thermal model to predict its performance and support the scale-up of the overall PYSOLO plant. Solid particles, such as sand, minerals or ceramic materials, are emerging as efficient and cost-effective heat transfer and storage media. They can withstand extremely high temperatures (up to 1000°C) and enable the transfer of heat for thermochemical processes. In order to identify the best suitable heat carriers for optimal heat storage and transfer, PYSOLO identified mechanical, thermal, optical and chemical properties for the downstream biomass pyrolysis.⁸

PYSOLO Project: Pioneering High-Temperature Solar Applications

The Horizon Europe project PYSOLO (PYrolysis of biomass by concentrated SOLar pOwer) investigates the potential of Concentrated Solar Thermal as driver of downstream heat-intensive biomass pyrolysis. By making use of CST in the biomass pyrolysis process, both the production of valuable renewable products such as bio-oil, biochar and pyrogas can be maximised, and the associated CO₂ emission minimised.

This offers economic and environmental benefits compared to conventional pyrolysis driven by heat derived from combustion of fossil carbon and fuels. While CST and renewable fuels based on pyrolysis products supports decarbonisation, char, bio-oil and pyrogas can also be used as renewable feedstock for the production of chemicals and materials thus fostering defossilisation of the chemical industry.

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